

Characterizing memory in atmospheric time series

An alternative approach based on renewal theory

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Abstract. Atmospheric dynamics originates persistent and/or intermittent structures spanning over several spatial and temporal scales. The dynamical instabilities trigger abrupt transitions between these meteorological structures. An approach based on the theory of renewal processes is proposed to describe these critical transition events. An alternative statistical analysis to qualitatively estimate the memory content of atmospheric time series is reviewed and an application to turbulence data in the Atmospheric Boundary Layer is illustrated. The connection between the proposed analysis and the assumption of a local flux-gradient relationship is also discussed.

1 Introduction

The atmosphere is a complex dynamical system described by strongly interacting dynamical variables. The resulting chaotic dynamical evolution generates coherent structures, intermittent (extreme) events or persistent motions in the atmospheric system. These structures are essentially unstable but, at the same time, are characterized by long life-times or, when considering extreme events, by long times of relatively quiescent motion. These time durations, being affected by several independent factors and by a chaotic non-linear dynamics, are essentially random variables whose statistical distribution can display a power-law decay over several decades. There are several examples of these kind of structures, such as the existence of persistent structures in meteorological fields at the synoptic scale [1] or the intermittent behavior of sweep-ejection events associated with the emergence of turbulent coherent structures in the Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL) [2, 3].

These structures are able to link relatively distant regions in a relatively short time, then giving a contribution to long range spatial correlations. Conversely, the long life-times or long inter-event times of these persistent structures also contribute to develop long range time correlations. Long range correlations are associated with an infinite correlation time or space scale. Considering only the temporal correlations, this can be written in the following way:

$$\tau_c = \int_0^{\infty} C(t) dt = +\infty, \quad (1)$$

where $C(t)$ is the stationary time correlation function. This is typically associated with the presence of a slow power-law decay in the correlation function: $C(t) \sim 1/t^\alpha$, $\alpha \leq 1$.

It is nowadays largely accepted that power law behavior emerges in complex systems, i.e., systems with a large number of degrees of freedom strongly interacting with each other on several temporal and spatial scales. However, the mechanisms giving rise to long range and

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power law behavior from these strong non-linear interactions are not yet well established. In particular, it is not clear if long range correlations and power-law behavior are associated with generic (universal) organizing principles of the complex systems. In spite of this, a common feature across many complex systems is increasingly documented, i.e., the burstiness of the system's activity patterns [4].

In dynamical systems theory, burstiness is related to the presence of a marginally unstable point. In the neighborhood of this kind of unstable points the dynamical map is not analytical, so that a Taylor's series cannot be written and, in particular, the standard linear stability analysis cannot be performed. In these cases a power-law behavior is often found: $\dot{x} \simeq \beta x^z, z > 1$. Typically, the system escapes slowly from the unstable point in a smooth way. Then, it reaches a chaotic region where the system's variables display a sudden transition to a different qualitative behavior, which is essentially a sort of chaotic burst. The non-linear behavior of the map in the neighborhood of the unstable point, related to burstiness, determines also an inverse power-law distribution of the escape times, corresponding to the times between two burst events. The simplest and most famous example of this kind of behavior, known as *Type-I intermittency*, is given by the Manneville map, which was investigated as a prototype for the alternance of laminar motion and chaotic bursts in turbulence [5].

A global description of the atmospheric dynamics should include a great number of strongly interacting degrees of freedom. A reduced statistical or chaotic model should reasonably involve averaged variables spanning over several temporal and spatial scales, thus generating long range (power-law) correlations and non-Gaussian distribution of fluctuations (Lévy flights, Lévy walks, Continuous Time Random Walks) [6,7]. This is typically associated with anomalous diffusion and anomalous scaling [8] and, especially, with the emergence of flux-gradient relationships that are non-local in time and/or space [9–13].

On the contrary, the modeling approach in atmospheric sciences is based on the assumption that local fluxes of mass, momentum, heat, etc... can be described as a function of the local gradient of some intensive property (concentration, flow strain, temperature, ...). The accuracy of this *locality assumption* is satisfactory when the central limit theorem's basic hypotheses are essentially fulfilled, and this can be related to short range (exponential) decay of space-time correlations. This is in agreement with Gaussian statistics of the meteorological (random) fields and with the so-called "normal scaling", defined as the linear increase of fluctuation's variance with time.

The local flux-gradient relationship is related to a local transport coefficient, defined as the ratio between the local flux and the local gradient, including the effect of sub-grid processes. The modeling or parameterization of transport coefficients is affected by the considered range of scales and usually follows from similarity considerations and semi-empirical relations between the averaged dynamical variables that are chosen as main representatives of the dynamics. The choice of the local variables relating to the local fluxes (directly or through their gradients) and of the associated characteristic scales is an assumption following from physical considerations. In spite of this, some arbitrariness is unavoidable and especially increases as the "locality assumption" becomes less and less accurate or, equivalently, as the influence of distant regions and/or previous history of the flow field becomes more and more important. This last condition is associated with the emergence of long range correlations, as defined by Eq. (1), and, then, by slow power-law decay.

In real situations, a correlation time is never infinite, but, in any case, it is possible to find some ranges of time lags with a slow power law decay. Apparently, the application of the locality assumption seems to be always possible, being associated with a finite correlation time. In this case, the local flux-gradient relationship should be applied to averaged variables with averaging time and/or volume slightly above the temporal and/or spatial correlation scales. However, fixed the time lag interval, the correlation time τ_c decreases as α increases, and the best condition should be given by an exponential decay. This means that, in the presence of slow power-law decay, the correlation time could be very large and the locality assumption could represent a too much rough approximation of real atmospheric dynamics, also because its range of validity could be too much different from the characteristic scales that need to be represented in the meteorological model. For example, this is known to happen when

considering the characteristic scales of the ABL: turbulent flows in vegetated or urban canopies, Convective Boundary Layer, etc. . . In this case, the inaccuracy of the locality assumption is sometimes evident from the emergence of a counter-gradient effect, i.e., of a negative transport coefficient [2]. In other cases the plausibility of this assumption is more ambiguous and the range of validity is not well defined.

Actually, a local flux-gradient relationship is highly preferred and usually applied in modeling studies involving atmospheric dynamics. This is probably due to a more clear physical meaning, which also allows to perform direct comparisons with experimental data, and, especially, to smaller computational costs in numerical models. However, the validity of the locality assumption is strongly dependent on the range of spatial and temporal scales represented by the model and, consequently, on the sub-grid processes included in the flux-gradient relationship. In fact, even if an equivalent description in terms of a *local non-homogeneous transport coefficient* is usually possible, the particular form of the *equivalent local model* can be strongly dependent from the mean meteorological conditions and other properties of the specific site. This could be the sign of the presence of long range correlations and anomalous scaling, emerging in a range of characteristic scales that is not only included in the sub-grid, but also in the resolved scales. Then, the memory or correlation properties of atmospheric motions represent a fundamental property that needs to be investigated in order to evaluate the accuracy of the locality assumption.

In order to investigate the aspects related to the validity of locality assumption, an approach based on *renewal theory* is here proposed. The main idea is that the emergence of coherent structures follows from the occurrence of random abrupt transitions in the atmospheric dynamics, from now on referred to as *critical events*. These structures are identified as meta-stable, or persistent, meteorological configurations with a random life-time. The renewal hypothesis is that the abrupt transitions are independent events and, consequently, the life-times, or Waiting Times (WTs), between two successive transitions are independent random variable, in agreement with the definition of a *renewal point process* [14]. Renewal processes are the basic ingredient for the development of Continuous Time Random Walk (CTRW) models of diffusion [6]. In these models the random walker (i.e., the diffusing variable) jumps only when a critical event occurs. Depending on the shape of WT distribution, this rule can determine an anomalous diffusion scaling and non-local flux-gradient relationship, whose dynamical origins are then associated with the critical events occurring randomly in time. However, the CTRW model includes the Gaussian diffusion as a particular case and, then, normal scaling: $x \sim t^{1/2}$; and exponential correlation decay: $C(t) \sim \exp(-t/\tau_c)$ [8]. In the CTRW model, Gaussian diffusion is based on a Poisson process, i.e., a renewal process with Poisson statistics of the number of events in a given time interval [15]. The Poisson process is the unique renewal process with an exponential WT distribution, whose decay rate is equal to the inverse correlation time: $r_0 = 1/\tau_c$.

The most important renewal process with Non-Poisson distribution of events is that one characterized by a power-law decay in the WT distribution: $\psi_0(\tau) \sim 1/\tau^\mu$. The renewal process with inverse power-law WT distribution is a basic model for the description of intermittency associated with anomalous diffusion. The walking rule where the WT represents the persistence of a dynamical variable leads to a corresponding CTRW model with a power-law decay in the correlation function with $\alpha = \mu - 2$ [16]. From Eq. (1) it is clear that the range associated with anomalous diffusion and non-locality is given by $\mu < 3$. A CTRW with $\mu > 3$ is not exactly Poissonian, but, in the long time limit, the asymptotic behavior of the diffusing variable is essentially Gaussian [8]. Consequently, Gaussian diffusion and exponential correlation are related to the condition $\mu > 3$ and, in this case, the locality assumption is a good approximation for the parameterization of the flux-gradient relationship. In this condition, the CTRW is said to belong to the basin of attraction of Gaussian diffusion.

Following this approach, the verification of the locality assumption is reduced to the analysis of the statistical properties of the WT sequences derived from the experimental time series. This work is then focused on the characterization of random events, described by the corresponding WT sequence. To this goal, the main features that need to be estimated are: (a) the distribution of life-times of a given atmospheric meta-stable or persistent structure (WTs between two critical events); (b) the presence of memory in the WT sequence. A power-law behavior in the WT distribution with power index $\mu < 3$ is a first condition for anomalous

behavior and non-local flux-gradient relationship. A second condition is given by the renewal property, i.e., the statistical independence of the WTs. A correlation analysis performed on the WT sequence is a first check of the renewal condition. However, it was shown that this analysis could be insensitive to the presence of some particular forms of memory related to Poisson and Non-Poisson events [15, 17–19]. This form of memory can be described in the context of renewal theory [14]. In fact, a power-law WT distribution can emerge in two different ways. It can be the consequence of Non-Poisson transition events, in agreement with a genuine renewal Non-Poisson process. Or it can emerge as the slow modulation of a Poisson process, i.e., a process that is locally Poisson, but with a time modulated decay rate $r(t)$. This property was exploited by Beck and coworkers [20, 21] to give a possible explanation for the emergence of power-law behavior in non-equilibrium stationary systems in terms of slow random fluctuations of the intensive parameter of a standard Gaussian process. A similar behavior could also be found in the atmospheric dynamics such as, for example, ABL turbulence modulated by synoptic meteorological motions, diurnal solar variations, etc...

The random modulation of an intensive parameter is hardly detected by a standard correlation analysis, thus introducing a hidden form of memory. In a non-homogeneous Poisson Process [22] the memory is included in the rate modulation, which cannot be observed directly. In the case of a completely random modulation, the standard correlation analysis is not able to detect this kind of memory.

For this reason, another approach, known as Renewal Aging analysis, has been proposed in recent years [15, 17–19]. The analysis of Renewal Aging, based on renewal theory [14], allows to estimate the content of memory generated by Non-Poisson and/or Poisson events. By exploiting some theoretical results about renewal Non-Poisson processes [23–25], Renewal Aging analysis can also give a qualitative indication of the presence of Non-Poisson events in the time series, even when these events are not observed directly but included in the rate modulation [18, 26, 27].

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 renewal theory will be briefly introduced. In Section 3 the analysis of Renewal Aging will be reviewed. In Section 4 a simple application to experimental observations of turbulence in the ABL will be illustrated and, finally, in Section 5 some conclusions will be summarized.

2 Renewal processes

A point process is defined as a series of events occurring randomly in time. Such a process is described by a sequence of increasing random times: $\{t_n\}$, $n = 1, 2, \dots$, $t_{n+1} > t_n$. The time instant $t_1 = 0$ is the time of the first event occurrence. Denoting the WTs by $\tau_n = t_{n+1} - t_n$, $n = 1, 2, \dots$, the process is defined to be renewal if the WTs τ_n are mutually independent random variables [14]. Under this assumption, the occurrence of an event is associated with a mechanism determining the basic property of erasing memory of the past.

A renewal process is uniquely defined by the statistical distribution of WTs or, equivalently, by the local rate of event production $r(t)$. Roughly speaking, the local rate $r(t)$ is the expected number of events per time unit in a neighborhood of the time t . More rigorously, following Cox [14] and assuming that the last event occurred at t_n , the local rate $r(t)$ is the (conditional) probability density that an event occurs in an infinitesimal time interval $[t, t + dt]$, given that no events occurred in the time interval $[t_n, t]$ ($t > t_n$):

$$r(t) = \lim_{dt \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{dt} \Pr \{t < t_{n+1} \leq t + dt \mid t_{n+1} > t\}. \quad (2)$$

By using the properties of conditional probabilities, it is possible to prove the following expression for the rate $r(t)$ [14]:

$$r(t) = \frac{\psi_0(t - t_n)}{\Psi_0(t - t_n)} = -\frac{1}{\Psi_0(t - t_n)} \frac{d\Psi_0}{dt}(t - t_n); \quad t_n < t < t_{n+1}, \quad (3)$$

being $\psi_0(\tau)$ the Probability Density Function of the WTs (WT-PDF) and:

$$\Psi_0(\tau) = \int_{\tau}^{\infty} \psi_0(s) ds = 1 - \int_0^{\tau} \psi_0(s) ds \quad (4)$$

the associated Survival Probability Function (WT-SPF), i.e., the probability that the WT $\tau_n = t_{n+1} - t_n$ is larger than τ . Clearly, it results: $\psi_0(t) = -d\Psi_0(t)/dt$. It is worth noting that the renewal condition is given by the independence of $\psi_0(\tau)$ (and $\Psi_0(\tau)$) from the index n labelling the n -th event and from the previous WTs. Once the rate function $r(t)$ is known, the WT-SPF is simply derived by solving Eq. (3) with respect to $\Psi_0(t)$ and imposing the initial condition $\Psi_0(t_n) = 1$:

$$\psi_0(\tau) = \exp\left(-\int_{t_n}^t r(t')dt'\right); \quad t_n \leq t < t_{n+1}. \quad (5)$$

For a Poisson process the WT-SPF is an exponential function: $\Psi_0(\tau) = \exp(-r_0\tau)$; so that, comparing with Eq. (5), it results that the event rate is constant in time: $r(t) = r_0$ [14]. This is in agreement with the well-known property that, in a Poisson process, the mean number of events in a given time interval $[t, t + \Delta t]$ is proportional to the length of the time interval itself: $\langle N[t, t + \Delta t] \rangle = r_0\Delta t$. A renewal Non-Poisson process is not only characterized by a Non-Poisson distribution of the events and a non-exponential WT distribution, but also by a changing in time event rate $r(t)$.

3 Renewal Aging and application to time series

The Renewal Aging method allows to characterize the memory features associated with the simultaneous presence of Poisson and Non-Poisson events and with the time modulation of a Poisson rate. In order to get this, the method exploits the basic properties of homogeneous Poisson processes, which do not show any aging, and of homogeneous Non-Poisson processes, which display a well-defined aging. Then, the renewal hypothesis is satisfied when the real aging of the time series corresponds to the aging of the renewal process with the same WT distribution, which is used as a sort of reference aging.

Qualitatively, the aging properties of a renewal process can be explained in the following way. Assuming that the observed renewal system is *prepared* at the initial time $t_0 = 0$, and that the observation starting time occurs at a later time $t = t_a$, then the statistical distribution of the first WT after the *aging time* t_a , named *aged WT*, is usually different from the distribution of the WTs following the first one. In general, these two WT distributions should be the same only when $t_a = 0$.

Due to the constant event rate, the aging time t_a has no effect for a Poisson process and, consequently, the WT distribution (PDF or SPF) is independent from t_a . As a consequence, the time-homogeneous Poisson process is the unique one in which the WT distribution doesn't change with t_a . Conversely, for renewal processes with non-exponential WT distribution, i.e., Non-Poisson renewal processes, the WT distribution is affected by the aging time t_a . Starting from this simple observation, the authors of Refs. [23–25] found general asymptotic results for the Aged WT distribution of a Non-Poisson renewal process with inverse power-law tail in the WT distribution:

$$\psi_0(\tau) \sim \frac{1}{\tau^\mu}; \quad \Psi_0(\tau) \sim \frac{1}{\tau^{\mu-1}}. \quad (6)$$

In particular, the following asymptotic behaviors were found:

$$\psi(\tau, t_a) \sim \frac{1}{\tau^{\mu-1}}; \quad \Psi(\tau, t_a) \sim \frac{1}{\tau^{\mu-2}}; \quad \tau < t_a. \quad (7)$$

$$\psi(\tau, t_a) \sim \frac{1}{\tau^\mu}; \quad \Psi(\tau, t_a) \sim \frac{1}{\tau^{\mu-1}}; \quad \tau > t_a. \quad (8)$$

A general analytical expression for the Aged WT distribution was found regardless of the particular shape of the brand new WT distribution [24, 25]. However, this expression is written in terms of infinite series and integrals and only the Laplace transform admits a closed analytical form; hence it is not suitable for a practical application in the evaluation of aged WT distributions, especially when dealing with real data. Nevertheless, this behavior of the Aged WT distribution can be exploited to investigate the correlation or memory structure of an

experimental WT sequence or, in some sense, its *amount of Renewal Aging*. The basic idea is to compare, for a range of t_a values, the aged distribution of the original WT sequence and the aged distribution of a WT sequence satisfying the renewal condition and having the same *young* or *brand new* WT distribution ($t_a = 0$). The aged distributions are computed from the aged WT sequences. These ones are derived from the young WT sequence by using an *aging algorithm*, which is a direct application of the definition of aging. Note that the aging property is derived as a statistical quantity associated with an ensemble of WT sequences. If such ensemble is directly available from the experimental data, the aging definition can be applied in a straightforward way. However, only a single WT sequence is usually available. As shown in Fig. 1, it is possible to build up an ensemble of sequences from the single experimental WT sequence. Note that, following this approach, some care must be taken in the interpretation of the results as, in general, the sequences in the ensemble are not statistically independent. In Fig. 1 it is also sketched the application of the aging algorithm to the single WT sequence. The experimental WT sequence is the first on the top of the figure and it is labelled with 1. The sequence labelled with 2 is obtained by removing the time interval between t_1 and t_2 , corresponding to the first WT τ_1 . By iteration, the sequence labelled with $n + 1$ is derived by taking off the n -th WT τ_n . Then, the *aged* or *truncated* WTs $\tau'_1, \tau'_2, \dots, \tau'_n, \dots$ are computed by superposing a time window of length t_a to the ensemble of sequences. Note that this is equivalent to a moving time window of length t_a that is not shifted at each time step or sampling time, but it is moved from event to event.

Fig. 1. Sketch of the aging algorithm applied to a single sequence of WTs, corresponding to the first sequence from the top.

More specifically, given the series of event occurrence times $\{t_n\}$, $n = 1, 2, \dots$, associated with the WT sequence $\tau_n = t_{n+1} - t_n$, the *aging algorithm* works as follows:

- Given the aging time t_a , represented by the double-arrow at the top of Fig. 1, a time window of length t_a is moved along the time series, jumping from event to event.
- Considering as starting time of the window the event time t_n , then the first event k ($k > n$) occurring after the end of the time window is found: $t_{k-1} < t_n + t_a < t_k$ (see the n -th sequence in Fig. 1).
- The aged (or truncated) WT is computed: $\tau'_n = \tau_n(t_a) = t_k - (t_n + t_a)$, and added to the sequence of aged WTs: $\{\tau_n(t_a)\}$, $n = 1, 2, \dots$.

Then, the analysis of Renewal Aging is performed in the following way:

- The *young* or *brand new* histogram (WT-PDF) and the WT-SPF are computed for the original WT sequence: $\psi_0(\tau)$, $\Psi_0(\tau)$.

- For given t_a , the *aging algorithm* is applied to the original WT sequence, obtaining the *real* sequence of *aged* WTs: $\{\tau_n^R(t_a)\}$, where the prime R stands for “Real”.
- A *renewal* sequence of WTs, $\{\tau_n^S\}$, is obtained from the original one by applying a random shuffling to the original (real) sequence of WTs. The prime S stands for “Shuffled”.
- The *renewal* sequence of *aged* WTs is obtained by applying the aging algorithm to the renewal sequence derived at the previous point: $\{\tau_n^S(t_a)\}$.
- The WT distributions are computed for the two aged WT sequences, getting the Aged Real WT-PDF and WT-SPF, $\psi^R(\tau, t_a)$ and $\Psi^R(\tau, t_a)$, and the Aged Shuffled (Renewal) WT-PDF and WT-SPF $\psi^S(\tau, t_a)$ and $\Psi^S(\tau, t_a)$.

In the following, Ψ^R and Ψ^S will be also named *Real Aging* and *Renewal Aging*, respectively. The three different WT distributions can be compared in a qualitative way to infer the amount of memory in the WT sequence and its Non-Poisson features. In fact, if the WT sequence is a renewal sequence even before the application of random shuffling, then the Aged Real and Aged Shuffled (Renewal) WT distributions coincide, and if the system is Non-Poisson, they are both different from the brand new WT distribution: $\psi^R(\tau, t_a) = \psi^S(\tau, t_a) \neq \psi_0(\tau)$ and $\Psi^R(\tau, t_a) = \Psi^S(\tau, t_a) \neq \psi_0(\tau)$.

The just described method for the analysis of Renewal Aging is essentially the same proposed and applied in the Refs. [15, 17, 18, 26], apart from the evaluation of $\psi^R(\tau, t_a)$ and $\psi^S(\tau, t_a)$, which was done by using and approximated analytical formula [24, 25]. In fact, the random shuffling, used here for the first time, is more accurate from a numerical point of view and has also the advantage of allowing to use a much larger range of the aging time t_a with respect to the analytical formula, whose applicability is essentially limited by the maximum observed value of WTs.

Recalling that a Non-Homogeneous Poisson process is defined as a process with a locally Poisson statistics whose rate is modulated in time, the interpretation of the results derived from the Renewal Aging analysis are related to the following important considerations and results [15, 17–19]:

1. For time-homogeneous Poisson processes there’s no aging: $\psi_0(\tau) = \Psi^R(\tau, t_a) = \Psi^S(\tau, t_a)$ and the same result is valid for WT-PDFs.
2. For time-homogeneous renewal Non-Poisson processes: $\Psi_0(\tau, t_a) < \Psi^R(\tau, t_a) = \Psi^S(\tau, t_a)$. This is the condition identifying a renewal process, but only if it is satisfied for any aging time $t_a > 0$.
3. For Non-Homogeneous Poisson Processes with a random rate modulation generating Non-Poisson events, the Real Aging $\Psi^R(\tau, t_a)$ decreases from the Renewal Aging $\Psi^S(\tau, t_a)$ to $\Psi_0(\tau, t_a)$ as the modulation becomes slower and slower. In other words, the Renewal Aging decreases as the ratio between Non-Poisson and Poisson events decreases.
4. Very slow modulation has zero Renewal Aging, which means $\Psi_0(\tau, t_a) = \Psi^R(\tau, t_a) \neq \Psi^S(\tau, t_a)$, even if the brand new WT distribution is not an exponential function but an inverse power-law.

4 Data analysis

The statistical analysis is here performed on experimental observations of turbulence in the ABL. In particular, the wind vertical velocity w and the concentration of Particulate Matter with size smaller of $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ (PM2.5) are considered. The choice is related to the role played by the fluctuations of these two quantities in air quality studies involving PM2.5 [28]. The data were collected in a measurement campaign carried out in Lecce during July 2003. The duration of the campaign is about 18 days. The instruments were mounted at the top of a telescopic mast (Clark Mast SQT9/M) at 9.6 m above the ground. The vertical velocity was measured with a ultrasonic anemometer Gill R3 operating at 100 Hz, whereas the PM2.5 concentration was observed by means of a optical aerosol detector pDR-1200 (MIE-Personal Data logging Real Time Aerosol Monitor) which operates at 1 Hz. Further details about the dataset and the instrumental aspects can be found in Ref. [28]. In order to compare the aging properties

Fig. 2. Sample of PM2.5 and vertical velocity data (about 3 days).

of the two time series, it is more appropriate to apply the Renewal Aging analysis with the same sampling time. For this reason, the velocity data were firstly averaged over 1 second time interval. In Fig. 2 two samples, extracted from the original data of vertical velocity (Panel a) and PM2.5 (Panel b), have been reported. As expected, a diurnal variation is evident from the vertical velocity data, whereas the PM2.5 concentration data are probably much more affected by the distribution and time evolution of the sources.

Now, having in mind the search for renewal Non-Poisson events, it is also suitable to cut off the modulation effects, already discussed in the Introduction, that are known *a priori*. In fact, it is well-known that turbulent motions in the ABL can be considered approximately stationary over time scales of about 30 minutes, but they become strongly non-stationary on time scales longer than 1 hour, and this is due especially to diurnal variations, but also to large scale (synoptic) meteorological motions. As said above, in the case of PM2.5 also the effect of sources has to be considered and, most probably, this could be the main modulation effect. A great part of this variability of ABL turbulence is known to be included in the first and second statistical moments, i.e., local trend of the mean wind and variance of the turbulence fluctuations.

Consequently, the time series of vertical velocity w and of PM2.5 concentration have been processed in order to eliminate the effect of the first two moments, which have been evaluated referring to time interval of 30 minutes. Firstly, it has been performed a linear detrending analysis. The linear trend, defined as: $\langle S \rangle(t) = at + b$, has been found by applying the least squares method to time interval of 30 minutes. The variance $\sigma^2(t)$ of the detrended fluctuations has been computed with an averaging time of 30 minutes. The resulting *normalized* time series is then defined as follows:

$$S_n(t) = \frac{S(t) - \langle S \rangle(t)}{\sigma(t)}, \quad (9)$$

where $S(t)$ is the original time series and $S_n(t)$ the normalized one. The normalized time series, corresponding to the samples of Fig. 2, are shown in Fig. 3.

In order to define a WT sequence, a definition of event must be introduced. A typical choice is given by the passages through a fixed threshold. After a preliminary analysis, a reasonable choice has been considered to be a threshold analysis on the signal variation, which is essentially the signal derivative, denoted as: $D(t) = S_n(t+1) - S_n(t)$. Then, an event is identified when the condition $|D(t)| > D_\tau$ is fulfilled, being D_τ the threshold value. The WT sequences have been derived from the normalized time series for different values of the threshold D_τ from 0.1 to 3.

The Renewal Aging analysis has been performed on these WT sequences and the main results are qualitatively illustrated in Figs. 4–6. In each figure the results of the analysis for the vertical velocity and the PM2.5 concentration are compared. It is worth noting that, looking at each single histogram (or WT-SPF), it is difficult to find a clearly defined inverse

Fig. 3. Same data of Fig. 2 after the application of the linear detrending and of the normalization using the local variance.

power-law function as the WT range in which this behavior emerges is not very large. However, as a general observation, it can be said that the estimated power index is given by the general pattern of the WT-SPFs derived for different threshold values. This is easily seen from Fig. 4 (both panels), where the brand new WT-SPF $\Psi_0(\tau)$ is shown for different threshold values and a power index almost independent from the threshold itself is found. Note that the fitted power indices are written as $\beta = \mu - 1$, in agreement with the expression of $\Psi_0(\tau)$ given in Eq. (6). In particular, the values $\mu = 2.8$ (vertical velocity) and $\mu = 2.5$ (PM2.5) seem to describe a general property of the WT-SPF that is almost independent from D_T in the range $D_T \sim 1 \div 3$. For values below $D_T = 1$, the power-law decay becomes less accurate and for $D_T = 0.1$, which is reported in Figs. 4 and 6, no evident power-law behavior is found.

Fig. 4. Brand new WT-SPF $\Psi_0(\tau)$ ($t_a = 0$) for different thresholds. The continuous lines represent the fitted inverse power-law functions $1/\tau^{\mu-1}$, where μ is reported in the figure for each line. The threshold from the bottom to the top SPF are: 0.1, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2.

The results of Fig. 4 for the brand new WT distribution could be sufficient to say that an anomalous behavior, corresponding to $\mu < 3$, emerges from the time series. However, in order to better understand the physical origin of the power-law behavior, it is appropriate to characterize also the memory properties, associated to intermittent events, by means of the Renewal Aging analysis. In Fig. 5a comparison between Real and Renewal Aging is shown for $t_a = 2000$ sec. and $D_T = 1$. In Fig. 6 the Aged Renewal WT-SPF, for $t_a = 2000$ sec. and for the same threshold values of Fig. 4, are displayed together with the associated inverse power-law fitting functions. In summary, it results that the renewal condition $\Psi^R = \Psi^S$ is never satisfied in an exact way, but, in the range $t_a > 1000$ sec. only a small decrease of Real Aging, with

Fig. 5. Comparison of Aged Renewal and Real WT-SPF $\Psi^S(\tau, t_a)$ and $\Psi^R(\tau, t_a)$ ($t_a = 2000$ sec.). The threshold value is $D_T = 1$. The Brand New WT-SPF $\Psi_0(\tau)$ is also reported as a reference curve.

Fig. 6. Aged Renewal WT-SPF $\Psi^S(\tau, t_a)$ ($t_a = 2000$ sec.) for different thresholds. The continuous lines represent the fitted inverse power-law functions $1/\tau^{\mu-2}$, where μ is reported in the figure for each line. The threshold from the bottom to the top SPF are: 0.1, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2.

respect to Renewal Aging, is seen. In the range $t_a < 1000$, the aging reduction is much more pronounced. This corresponds to the presence of strong memory between the events in the range of relatively short times.

The condition emerging in Fig. 5 could be associated to a Poisson system whose rate is modulated by another system with Non-Poisson events [15,19]. However, when the aging reduction is small, it is appropriate to consider also the aspects related to the definition of event, which is obviously not exact. In fact, the identification of the events is a delicate point and the threshold analysis is expected to detect also some spurious events, i.e., events associated to the statistical analysis and not to the real dynamical transitions. As a consequence, if the aging reduction is small, it is reasonable to assume that it is associated with the statistical errors included in the event's identification.

In Fig. 6 the estimated power indices are written as $\alpha = \mu - 2$, and the corresponding estimated values of μ are indicated in both panels in order to underline the difference with respect to a renewal process with inverse power-law WT distribution. In fact, for a renewal process with WT distribution satisfying Eq. (6), it is expected from Eqs. (6) and (7) that the power indices indicated in Fig. 6 would be equal to those reported in Fig. 4. On the contrary, there are small, but not negligible, differences: $\mu = 2.8$ and $\mu = 3.1$ for vertical velocity; $\mu = 2.5$ and $\mu = 2.7$ for PM2.5 ($D_T \geq 1.5$). An important aspect to be considered is that the evaluation of the power-law behavior is more ambiguous and less accurate for the Aged WT-SPF with respect to the brand new WT-SPF and this could be an additional source of error in the analysis.

However, this gives an additional information about the level of accuracy of the assumption of an inverse power-law WT distribution.

5 Concluding remarks

The statistical analysis of Renewal Aging has been proposed as a tool for evaluating the memory content of atmospheric time series and an application to available turbulence data has been illustrated. The Renewal Aging analysis was derived in the framework of renewal theory [14]. It was argued that this analysis is sensitive to the ratio between Poisson and Non-Poisson critical events, and this represents an interesting aspect with respect to standard correlation analysis. This approach can improve the characterization of the memory features of systems generating intermittent events with inverse power-law WT distribution, which usually emerge in chaotic systems with strong non-linear interactions.

The atmosphere is a good candidate for this kind of behavior, due to the presence of persistent and/or intermittent meta-stable structures, spanning on several time scales, from a few minutes (ABL turbulence, coherent eddies, sweep-ejection structures) to inter-annual climate variability. In particular, the time intermittent structure of ABL turbulence was here investigated, comparing vertical velocity and PM2.5 data. The analysis showed a slightly greater anomalous behavior of PM2.5 with respect to vertical velocity. As PM2.5 is advected by the turbulence field, the small difference in the anomalous index μ could be related to the internal dynamics of the PM2.5, such as coagulation and nucleation processes. Actually, the time evolution of sources could also affect the power-law decay of PM2.5.

An interesting aspect is that, even after the detrending and the normalization of the time series, a small residual memory in the time series is present, as it is seen from the finding of a small aging reduction for aging time t_a greater than 2000 sec. This could be interpreted as a weak effect related to modulating large scale meteorological persistent motions, but it can be also determined by the inaccuracy in the threshold analysis used for the event's identification. The evaluation of the threshold is a crucial aspect. Here, no exact *a priori* evaluation of the threshold was made, apart from the choice of a maximum value of about 3, chosen after the qualitative analysis of Fig. 3. The *a posteriori* criterion used here was the reasonable requirement that the results should be almost independent from the threshold value, at least in an extended range of values. As said in Section 4, this range was found to be: $D_T \sim 1 \div 3$. In this range, the effects of both the threshold and the modulating large scale motions are small. This seems to confirm that a great part of the modulating effects are included in the first two statistical moments (trend and variance) and that the turbulence dynamics is essentially characterized by renewal Non-Poisson events.

Finally, it is important to remark that Renewal Aging analysis should be thought as an additional statistical analysis, to be used in conjunction with standard correlation analysis, which could improve the characterization of memory in a time series. This approach could also give some effort in the study of Extreme Events in meteorology and climatology, in weather classification schemes and in the modelling of non-Gaussian and non-local closures for turbulent fluxes. However, further investigations are needed for a better characterization of the results of Renewal Aging analysis and for a better quantification of the error made by applying a local closure for the flux-gradient relationship.

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